

Hybrid Provision of Energy based on Reliability and Resiliency by Integration of Dc Equipment

Work Package WP7
German Pilot

Deliverable D7.1
Report on the demo site grid setups

Funding Instrument: Innovation Action
Call: H2020-LC-SC3-2020-EC-ES-SCC
Call Topic: LC-SC3-ES-10-2020 - DC – AC/DC hybrid grid for a modular, resilient and high RES share grid development

Project Start: 1 October 2020
Project Duration: 48 months

Beneficiary in Charge: RWTH Aachen

Document Identifier: doi:[10.5281/zenodo.14262702](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14262702)

Dissemination Level		
PU	Public	✓
PP	Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)	
RE	Restricted to a group specified by the Consortium (including the Commission Services)	
CO	Confidential, only for members of the Consortium (including the Commission Services)	

Deliverable Information

Document Administrative Information	
Project Acronym:	HYPERRIDE
Project Number:	957788
Deliverable Number:	D7.1
Deliverable Full Title:	Report on the demo site grid setups
Deliverable Short Title:	Demo site grid setups
Document Identifier:	HYPERRIDE-D71-DemoSiteGridSetups-submitted
Beneficiary in Charge:	RWTH Aachen
Report Version:	v1.7
Contractual Date:	30/03/2024
Report Submission Date:	20/11/2024
Dissemination Level:	PU
Nature:	Report
Lead Author(s):	J. Mathé, K. Hetzenecker (RWTH Aachen)
Co-author(s):	
Keywords:	Hybrid Grid Control, Centralized Control, MVDC, DAB, European Union (EU), H2020 Project, HYPERRIDE, GA 957788
Status:	_ draft, _ final, _x_ submitted

Change Log

Date	Version	Author/Editor	Summary of Changes Made
18/03/2024	v1.0	J. Mathé (RWTH Aachen)	Initial draft
20/05/2024	v1.1	S. Costea (EATON)	Internal review
24/06/2024	v1.2	J. Mathé (RWTH Aachen)	Update after review
11/07/2024	v1.3	G. Jambrich (AIT)	CO-Review 1
28/08/2024	v1.4	J. Mathé (RWTH Aachen)	Update according template
17/09/2024	v1.5	G. Jambrich (AIT)	CO-Review 2
04/11/2024	v1.6	J. Mathé, K. Hetzenecker (RWTH Aachen)	Update according template
20/11/2024	v1.7	G. Jambrich (AIT)	Final version

Table of Contents

Executive Summary	7
1. Introduction	8
1.1 Purpose and Scope of the Document	8
1.2 Structure of the Document	8
2. The RWTH Hybrid Grid	9
2.1 Medium Voltage Part	9
2.2 Low Voltage Part.....	10
2.3 Introduction of Converters.....	11
3. High Level Grid Control	16
3.1 Grid Server.....	17
3.2 Grid Editor.....	19
3.3 Device Connection	20
3.4 Grid Server Computer.....	22
4. Grid Protection	23
4.1 Low Voltage AC	23
4.2 Medium Voltage AC.....	23
4.3 DC Grids.....	23
4.4 FPGA Based Safety Loop.....	26
5. Grid Operations	28
5.1 DAB1 Converter	28
5.2 IGBT DAB3 Converter.....	29
5.3 Potential Grid Structures.....	30
5.4 Hybrid Grid Testing.....	31
5.5 RWTH Demo-Site Workshop September 2023	32
6. Conclusions	34
References	35

List of Figures

Figure 1: Overview of the RWTH hybrid grid.	9
Figure 2: Cable route of the MVDC grid at Campus Melaten.	10
Figure 3: Overview of the GE Testbench with 2.5 MVA AFE and IGBT DAB3.	11
Figure 4: Overview of the Modular DAB3 converter.	13
Figure 5: View into the DAB1 converter.	13
Figure 6: Electrical part of the two LVAC AFEs.	14
Figure 7: Overview of interfaces between Grid Server and devices.	17
Figure 8: Control states defined in the unified converter control structure.	19
Figure 9: Grid Editor while constructing a grid.	19
Figure 10: DAB1 control window.	20
Figure 11: STM32 MCU board with Ethernet capability.	21
Figure 12: DC fault current and voltage shape.	24
Figure 13: DAB1 MV side with additional press-pack diodes in foreground.	25
Figure 14: Schematic of the DAB1 converter with additional free-wheeling diodes.	25
Figure 15: LVDC circuit breaker concept.	26
Figure 16: FPGA based safety loop.	27
Figure 17: DAB1 converter load step at LVDC side.	28
Figure 18: GE P80i programming interface.	29
Figure 19: Newly created control blocks for IGBT DAB3.	29
Figure 20: IGBT DAB3 waveforms; ac current (green), primary side transformer voltage (yellow), secondary side transformer voltage (blue), dc current (purple).	30
Figure 21: Grid structure as presented during RWTH demo-site workshop in September 2023.	31
Figure 22: Hybrid grid simulation model from Deliverable WP4.7 (2023).	32
Figure 23: Test setup with 2.5 MVA AFE and DAB1 converter.	32
Figure 24: RWTH demo-site workshop meeting in September 2023.	33
Figure 25: Exemplary measurements taken during the RWTH demo-site workshop ac current (red / green / blue), dc current (light blue), dc voltage (purple / yellow).	33

List of Tables

Table 1: Electrical data of the 2.5 MVA AFE.....	11
Table 2: Electrical data of the IGBT DAB3.	12
Table 3: Electrical data of Modular DAB.	12
Table 4: Electrical data of the DAB1.	14
Table 5: Electrical data of one LVAC AFE converter.....	14
Table 6: Device connection types.	22

List of Abbreviations

ac	Alternating Current
AFE	Active Front End
CWD	Center for Wind Power Drives
DAB	Dual Active Bridge
DAB3	Three-phase Dual Active Bridge
dc	Direct Current
FPGA	Field Programmable Gate Array
GE	General Electric
GUI	Graphical User Interface
ICT	Information and Communication Technologies
IGBT	Isolated Gate Bipolar Transistor
LVAC	Low Voltage AC
LVDC	Low Voltage DC
MCU	Microcontroller Unit
MVAC	Medium Voltage AC
MVDC	Medium Voltage DC
OSI	Open Systems Interconnection
PCB	Printed Circuit Board
PEBB	Power Electronics Building Block
PGS	Institute for Power Generation and Storage Systems
RWTH	Rheinisch-Westfälische Technische Hochschule
TCP	Transmission Control Protocol
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

Deliverable D7.1 is a report on the work done to adapt the RWTH pilot hybrid grid to allow for new grid setups and validation of grid operation. It describes the available devices for grid operation as well as the newly designed control software. A fault analysis is conducted for the individual grid parts and the operation of the grid is finally demonstrated under the scope of the RWTH demo-site workshop meeting in September 2023.

The report details all available devices for grid operation and gives electrical details. The current state of the devices is stated, and necessary work for grid operation is summed up. Also, the grid structure of the RWTH hybrid grid is introduced.

In addition, a centralized control software for grid operation is introduced. The concept of this software is explained, and connection interfaces between this software and the grid devices are discussed. Furthermore, the implementation of these interfaces is explained. For the RWTH hybrid grid, a fault analysis for every grid part was conducted. Possible fault scenarios are considered, and solution for grid protection are discussed separately. Specifically, dc grid protection without dc circuit breakers is discussed, and a suitable protection concept is introduced.

Finally, preparations for the hybrid grid operation is discussed. The final grid structure is introduced, and commissioning work is given exemplarily for two devices.

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose and Scope of the Document

The purpose of task 7.1 is the preparation of the RWTH Aachen hybrid medium and low voltage ac and dc grid for new grid setups. On the electrical side, the existing grid infrastructure will be modified to allow for flexible test setups and integration of additional grid devices. This is accomplished by extending the functionalities of the grid equipment such as converters as well as by creating flexible device interconnections. Preliminary simulations of the grid thereby ensure a stable operation. To allow for a safe grid operation in case of a fault, possible fault scenarios are investigated and a protection concept is developed for both medium and low voltages. In addition, possible test scenarios for the hybrid circuit breaker developed in task 3.9 are considered during the preparation. Furthermore, in preparation of task 7.3, the Direct Current (dc) Measurement Unit developed in task 3.10 will be integrated into one converter.

Besides the adaption of hardware and simulation, the network infrastructure will be updated to allow for grid device connection and communication to a central control computer. The control software of the grid devices is extended with a new control layer, allowing for reliable high-level control and automation. New software is developed for controlling grid devices under different grid configurations. In preparation of tasks 7.4 and 7.5, the software creates an abstraction layer of the grid for multiple operators as well as the ICT automation architecture defined in Work Package (WP) 5.

Finally, the functionality of the hybrid grid will be evaluated and various operation strategies are tested. Interactions with the newly developed control layer and software are verified and preparations for the upcoming task 7.2 are finalized

1.2 Structure of the Document

The structure of this report is outlined in the followings. Section 2 presents the RWTH hybrid medium and low voltage ac and dc grid and gives an overview of the grid status. The individual converters are presented, and possible setups for grid operation are defined.

Section 3 explains the high-level control of the converters in more detail. The individual interfaces are summed up, and the concept of a generic control server is introduced. The user interface to control the grid is discussed as well.

Section 4 investigates different fault scenarios that can occur inside the RWTH hybrid grid. Simulations are shown, and concepts for protecting the grid are discussed.

Section 5 shows the grid operation, as it was presented in the RWTH demo site workshop meeting in Sep. 2023. The RWTH hybrid grid is shown under operation, with the achievements from Sections 2 to 4 used.

2 The RWTH Hybrid Grid

The German pilot is a hybrid medium and low voltage grid consisting of ac and dc sub-parts. The grid itself is made up of a multitude of different converter systems, connecting the different voltage levels as well as providing an interface between ac and dc. Figure 1 gives an overview about the converters used inside the German pilot and their connection. Medium voltage dc connections are drawn in orange, while low voltage dc lines are drawn in blue. All Alternating Current (ac) lines are drawn in dark grey. While the connection to the medium voltage ac is a commercial system, the systems used for medium voltage dc as well as low voltage ac and dc are build up or modified by the institute. For these converters, the operation can be fully controlled by the operator.

Figure 1: Overview of the RWTH hybrid grid.

2.1 Medium Voltage Part

The Medium Voltage DC (MVDC) part (see Figure 1) of the German pilot is connected by a 2.5 MVA Active Front End (AFE) to the 3.3 kV Medium Voltage AC (MVAC) public grid. It is one part of a larger test-bench built by General Electric (GE), which is shown in Figure 3. While another part is used to drive a test bed for large electric drives up to 5 MW, the remaining two parts were connected by a medium frequency transformer to form an IGBT high power Three-phase Dual Active Bridge (DAB3). In addition, the medium voltage dc (MVDC) part consists of a 1.1 km long dc grid, connecting the test facilities at Institute for Power Generation and Storage Systems (PGS) to the Center for Wind Power Drives (CWD) in the middle of the RWTH Campus Melaten. Figure 2 shows the MVDC cable route at the RWTH Campus. At CWD side, the connection to the high power electrical drivetrain is currently in the planning phase and therefore no power can be fed between the two institutes. However, the laid cable can be used as a 2.2 km long loop to simulate an actual dc grid without interfering with test procedures at other RWTH institutes.

Figure 2: Cable route of the MVDC grid at Campus Melaten.

The voltage of the MVDC part is fixed to 5 kV by the 2.5 MVA AFE. However, when using the IGBT DAB3, the voltage on the other converter side can be chosen freely if not connected in a loop. For example, precharging this side from the Low Voltage DC (LVDC) side is possible and a proper use case.

The MVDC part of the German pilot is connected by two dc to dc converter systems to the LVDC part. Both systems are Dual Active Bridge (DAB) converters, but following different design approaches. One converter is a single phase DAB (DAB1), while the other uses a modular concept (Modular DAB3). Due to their topology, both converters provide galvanic isolation and slightly adjustable voltages at both ports.

2.2 Low Voltage Part

The LVDC part is connected by the aforementioned converter systems to the MVDC grid of the German pilot. Within the LVDC part, no converter system can provide additional galvanic isolation to the system. Therefore, the two Low Voltage AC (LVAC) AFE converters connected to low voltage ac (LVAC) are equipped with additional three phase ac transformers. These transformers have a winding ration of 1:1.

The LVAC grid is supplied as three-phase, 400 V, ac power inside the German pilot. It is connected to the 10 kV medium voltage ac (MVAC) by a standard ac transformer. Depending on the systems used, the LVAC connections can be switched by manual LVAC switchgear contactors.

For the LVDC part, all converters are connected to a common dc bus. The voltage of this bus is mainly determined by the two LVAC AFE converters, and was set to 700 V. This voltage is also in accordance with (Current OS Standard (2024)). Within the LVDC bus, no switching is possible, and converters are disconnected by removal of the devices power cables when not in use.

2.3 Introduction of Converters

To provide a better overview about the individual converter systems and their functional restrictions that need to be overcome by WP 7.1, a brief introduction of every system used is given in the next section.

2.3.1 GE 2.5 MVA Active Front End

The GE 2.5 MVA AFE connects the 3.3 kV ac internal grid to the 5 kV bus inside the GE converter system. It shares its dc-link capacitors with a motor drive unit and another dc to ac converter. Therefore, the build-in capacitance of this converter is higher than for similar converters of this power rating. Figure 3 gives an overview over the complete converter system, including the secondary side of the IGBT DAB3 converter.

Figure 3: Overview of the GE Testbench with 2.5 MVA AFE and IGBT DAB3.

Table 1: Electrical data of the 2.5 MVA AFE.

Parameter	Value
Topology	3-level AFE with IGBTs
AC Voltage	3.3 kV
DC Voltage	5 kV
Maximum Power	2.5 MVA
Switching Frequency	600 Hz
Line Filter	Inductive

As the AFE is the only converter capable of connecting to MVAC, it controls the MVAC switchgear as well as the cooling infrastructure of the overall system. In addition, it is responsible for checking safety relevant data like access doors to the test hall. It was therefore decided that this part of the converter system should not be modified at all, and the existing user interface will be used during testing of the medium voltage part.

The voltage of this converter is fixed to 5 kV, which also defines the voltage for the three aforementioned converters. Its dc side is precharged by a build-in precharge circuit, which is activated by the systems startup procedure. This procedure cannot be changed, but for testing purposes an external voltage can be supplied to the internal dc-bus. Table 1 gives an overview over the electrical data of the 2.5 MVA AFE.

2.3.2 Three-phase IGBT DAB

This system is a high power three-phase three-level dual active bridge system and connects to MVDC lines at a rated voltage of 5 kV each. It was build up in a previous project from two dc to ac converter blocks, which share the same topology as this of the active front end and belong to the GE testbench (see Figure 3). A medium frequency transformer connects the two ac sides of the two blocks used, allowing bidirectional power flow and galvanic isolation. One side of the converter shares its dc-link with the AFE, which fixes the voltage at this side to 5 kV. The other side has its own dc-link, and can be set to any voltage up to the nominal voltage of the converter. However, due to the low stray inductance of the medium frequency transformer, the two voltages must not deviate more than 20 %. This range can be extended by changing the modulation scheme, which is not under the scope of WP 7.1. Table 2 shows the electrical parameters of the IGBT DAB3

Table 2: Electrical data of the IGBT DAB3.

Parameter	Value
Topology	3-level 3-phase Dual Active Bridge
Nominal Voltage	5 kV (both sides)
Maximum Power	5 MW
Switching Frequency	1 kHz
Transformer Ration	1:1

2.3.3 Modular three-phase Dual Active Bridge

This system is one of two converters, which allow the interconnection of MVDC and LVDC. It was built up from eight identical modules, each with an input voltage of 625 V. The input side of all modules is then connected in series, giving the nominal input voltage of 5 kV (see Figure 4). On the low voltage side, the outputs of the eight modules can be connected in three different ways. For the connection of the converter into the hybrid grid, two sets of four parallel connected modules are connected in series, giving an output voltage of 700 V. This voltage is symmetrical around ground potential. Medium frequency transformers in each individual module provide galvanic isolation between medium and low voltage sides. The electrical parameters for the modular DAB3 converter are given in Table 3.

Table 3: Electrical data of Modular DAB.

Parameter	Value
Topology	Modular 3-phase Dual Active Bridge
MVDC Side Voltage	5 kV
LVDC Side Voltage	350 V / 700 V / 1400 V
Maximum Power	320 kW
Switching Frequency	10 kHz

Figure 4: Overview of the Modular DAB3 converter.

Each module is controlled by one of eight control systems, which can be programmed by using the PLECS Coder plugin. Each system features a high-speed data link to connect all systems with each other. However, these systems were never designed to communicate with systems outside their converter.

2.3.4 Single-phase Dual Active Bridge

The other converter that is used for interconnecting MVDC and LVDC is a single-phase DAB with a maximum power of 100 kW. It was originally designed to connect a medium voltage, 5 kV, battery storage system to the low voltage ac grid (Thomas (2014)). It features an overall transformer ratio of 1:10, however, due to the used modulation scheme, the voltages at both sides can be freely selected within their operating ranges. Table 4 shows the electrical parameters of the DAB1 converter.

Figure 5: View into the DAB1 converter.

The system is controlled by a custom built controller, which features only one serial interface for external communication. The interface itself is galvanically isolated by fiber-optical transceivers.

The converter was built up by the institute and was modified over time to suit different applications. When it was built, it was the first converter of its kind in the given voltage range. Figure 5 shows a picture of the converter hardware.

Table 4: Electrical data of the DAB1.

Parameter	Value
Topology	Single-phase Dual Active Bridge
MVDC Side Voltage	5 kV
LVDC Side Voltage	700 V
Maximum Power	100 kW
Switching Frequency	1 KHz
Transformer Ratio	1:5

2.3.5 Low Voltage Active Front Ends

Interconnection of the MVDC bus to the LVAC grid is done by two 50 kW three level inverters. The systems were built within the institute from two Semikron Power Electronics Building Block (PEBB) and additional ac filtering. Two 1:1 transformers provide galvanic isolation to the grid in order to avoid parasitic current flow through their earth connection. An overview schematic of the converter is given in Figure 6. Table 5 gives the electrical parameters of one LV AFE.

Figure 6: Electrical part of the two LVAC AFEs.

Table 5: Electrical data of one LVAC AFE converter.

Parameter	Value
Topology	3-level AFE with IGBTs
AC Voltage	400 V
DC Voltage	700 V
Maximum Power	50 kW
Switching Frequency	8 kHz

Every system is controlled by a Texas Instrument LaunchPad based MCUs which can be programmed from PLECS. Connection to other systems is provided by using the onboard CAN interface, which can be controlled directly from inside the PLECS software.

2.3.6 Medium Voltage DC Switchgears

To interconnect the different MVDC converter system with each other as well as to the FEN dc grid, four switchgear cabinets were installed during the construction of the dc grid. The

switchgear cabinets are equipped with WAGO Modbus bus coupler systems for reading out measurement data and controlling the medium voltage switches.

3 High Level Grid Control

All of the aforementioned systems were originally designed to be operated by a single operator and a unique control interface. While some of those control interfaces are independent of a specific control computer, some interfaces require specific hardware and software. In addition, no interface was designed with interoperability in mind, and no communication was possible between individual devices at the beginning of task 7.1. During previous grid operations, the operators of the different converters had to communicate with each other, which proved sub-optimal for a reliable and safe operation. An optimal solution should therefore bundle the data from all devices, making it easier for one or multiple operators to interact with the grid.

To allow for a fast and easy connection of multiple converters, the interfaces of these converters have to be unified as well. Several communication interfaces allow the connection of multiple devices to one bus. A list of possible interfaces is given below.

- RS485 : Industry standard bus system (refer to RS-485 Standard (1998)) using bidirectional communication between multiple system. It offers data rates up to 10 Mbit and is easy to implement.
- CAN : Mainly used in automotive applications, but also seen in industrial application (refer to CANopen Standard (1995)). It offers data rates up to 1 Mbit and can be implemented even in smaller systems.
- Ethernet : Ethernet (IEEE 802.3, Ethernet Standard (2020)) is well known from computer networking, but also used in industrial applications in various forms. It offers data rates up to several 100 GBit if needed. While point to point connections can use any protocol, the IP standard needs to be implemented when using existing infrastructure.

All of these interfaces have distinct benefits and drawbacks to them. The selection of one interface is driven by finding the optimum of implementation time, data rate, and infrastructure costs.

As real-time data transfer and control is hard if not impossible to implement in some of the existing system controllers, it was decided that all systems should operate standalone. When connected to a common electrical bus, these connections should follow a common ruleset like nominal voltage or droop control. This avoids expensive buildup of redundancy data communication and allows system operation with lost communication. In addition, this would maintain stability of the grid in case of hypothetical cyber-attacks.

Without any high-speed communication needed, the data rates can be chosen quite low, as only status data needs to be transmitted periodically. With update rates of 100 ms, even the lowest data rates offered by CAN are sufficient for this use case. Therefore, the interface must be selected by implementation time and infrastructure cost.

The implementation of the aforementioned interfaces is another major point, as implementing and debugging these is time consuming. While RS485 and CAN are relatively easy to implement, they only offer OSI layer 1 (physical layer) or 2 (data transfer layer) data transfer. In both cases, an additional protocol need to be implemented to get data from a sender to a specific receiver. This is the same for Ethernet communication, however, when using the IP standard, this is handled by the IP stack. Nowadays, several open-source IP stack like lwIP exists, which resolves the issue of implementing the IP standard. A test with an Ethernet capable MCU board from ST Microelectronics has shown that Ethernet communication can be set up within 1 h.

The major benefit of Ethernet communication is the availability of network equipment. On one hand, the existing infrastructure inside the German pilot test hall can be used. On the other hand, missing equipment is cheap and easily available. For later, long term installation or field tests, more rugged hardware can be bought from several manufacturers. It was therefore decided to use Ethernet communication for connecting the individual grid components to a central control system. For systems which cannot be upgraded directly with an Ethernet connection, a small interface converter module was planned. In the future, more and more converters used by the institute will have a direct Ethernet connection, so these interface converters will only see short term usage. An overview about the planned communication structure from the Grid Server (Section 3.1) to the individual devices is shown in Figure 7.

Figure 7: Overview of interfaces between Grid Server and devices.

To transmit actual data over the Ethernet connection, it was decided to use the Modbus TCP protocol where possible. This protocol was chosen because some devices already featured an implementation or could be easily upgraded, reducing overall implementation time.

3.1 Grid Server

The main element of the centralized control structure is the so called Grid Server. It communicates on one side with all electrical systems inside the grid, and on the other side with multiple user interfaces. The Grid Server is a standalone software, which currently only runs under a Windows based operating system. Its main purpose is to collect periodic measurement data from all connected devices and distributes them to the operator. In the other direction, the Grid Server forwards setpoints and commands to the grid devices.

Prior to operation, the Grid Server must receive a list of all available and used devices inside the grid. This is done by one operator, who needs to upload a configuration of the grid. This configuration contains all devices, as well as how these are connected, and additional relevant data. Currently, the Grid Server supports 5 different types of elements, which can be seen in Figure 9:

- Node : A node is an electrical line to which other elements can be connected. For easier operation, nodes can have names that can be displayed inside the user interface
- Converter : Converters are connected between two nodes, which do not necessarily need to have the same voltage level nor type.
- Switchgear : This represents a switchgear which was built up during the FEN dc grid construction. They are always connected to MVDC.

- Breaker : Currently, only the sub-class of a MVDC breaker is implemented. A breaker always breaks all lines, regardless of how many mechanical switches were actually used. Breakers are connected to the same type of node on both sides.
- Source : For constant or non-controllable sources inside the grid. A source can be ac or dc, as well as medium or low voltage.

The Grid Server reads in the list of used elements and builds up an internal representation of the grid. This allows the internal representation of the grid devices to interact with each other. For example, any breaker can get the line voltage on either side from connected converters. Therefore, switching can be prohibited if both sides show different voltages, adding additional safety to the grid operation.

For connecting the Grid Server with the defined grid devices, every element read in by the server carries additional information. Currently, two interfaces are programmed and tested for communicating with the devices. The first one is Modbus TCP, which is used to connect to some converters as well as the MVDC switchgears. The second one is Beckhoff ADS, a protocol developed by Beckhoff to communicate to TwinCAT and their control systems. ADS is used to communicate to some converters that were not equipped with Modbus Interfaces (see Table 6).

The Grid Server is programmed in such a way, that every grid device behaves, dependent on its type, the same. Therefore, every device presents the same interface, regardless of its power or voltage level. This is especially important for converters, which were originally operated by a multitude of different interfaces and protocols. Furthermore, the development process is speed up, allowing a new converter to be tested against an existing implementation of the communication. Therefore, for new devices, only one side needs to be programmed and debugged. It also simplifies the grid structure creation in software, as the operator does not need to know all details about the device connection.

On its other side, the Grid Server can be accessed by up to 16 TCP connection, allowing several operators and others systems to control the server and read out data. The protocol was already implemented in the software used in WP 7.5.

3.1.1 Unified Converter Control Structure

As already stated above, all converters in the demo-site used different communication protocols and control software. To unify the converter control, a unified converter control structure was defined. This control structure includes all relevant data for the converter operation and was implemented on every converter. It allows the Grid Server and Grid Editor (see Section 3.2) to communicate with every device in the same way and simplifies extension of the grid. For the user, it simplifies the creation of the grid, as the user does not need to have internal knowledge about the used communication protocols and converter features.

The structure also defines operating modes, which are used for grid operation, as well as how the converter should change between these modes (see Figure 8). A static data-field inside the structure gives the availability of the different modes, so converters do not have to feature every mode if not needed or possible.

Lastly, the structure includes current measurement data of the device, which is displayed inside the Grid Editor to the user. The data is also used by the Grid Server to forward it to other devices like switchgears or circuit breakers.

Figure 8: Control states defined in the unified converter control structure.

3.2 Grid Editor

To allow for a fast and easy method of creating new grid configurations, another application, called the Grid Editor, was developed under the scope of WP7.1. The Grid Editor serves two main purposes, namely the aforementioned creation of grid configurations as well as the control of an already set-up grid. For both use-cases, the Grid Editor serves as a Graphical User Interface (GUI).

Figure 9: Grid Editor while constructing a grid.

For generating a new grid configuration, different components can be instantiated inside the Grid Editor. The components can then be configured and named accordingly in a separate window. To form an actual grid, the Grid Editor allows the interconnection of the individual components by lines and junctions. The generated grid configuration can be stored in .json file format, making swapping between different configurations as easy as possible. Figure 9 shows the Grid Editor during grid configuration.

The generated grid configuration is then uploaded by the Grid Editor to the Grid Server. If a configuration was already uploaded by another operator, this configuration can be overwritten if

the grid is not in use. If multiple users work together operating on one grid, an already uploaded configuration can also be downloaded. The configuration will look the same on every instance of the Grid Editor.

After uploading the grid configuration to the Grid Server, the grid can be started by the operator. In the following, the Grid Editor switches from “edit” into “view” mode. In this mode, the configuration of the individual elements cannot be changed anymore. However, for controllable systems, the systems control window is shown instead. Furthermore, additional information is shown in the main window. For example, converters will show their transferred power as well as the direction of the power flow.

Inside the systems control window, the individual devices show additional information and allow full control over their functionality. However, due to the limitations some systems have, not all functions might be available to the operator. For converters, a read-only field in the systems data array determines the available functions of the system. Devices can be controlled by different user inputs. Switchgears present an overview schematic, where switches can be opened and closed by clicking directly into the schematic itself. Converters, however, need to be supplied with additional data like reference voltage and operating mode, which can be set by entry boxes and buttons. Regardless of their types, all elements show relevant live-data inside their control window. Figure 10 shows the control window of an exemplary converter during operation.

Figure 10: DAB1 control window.

3.3 Device Connection

The connection from the Grid Server to the individual grid devices is a major element within the grid control structure. While some devices inherently support Modbus TCP, several devices need to be equipped with network connection and protocol implementation.

For the 5 MW IGBT DAB3, the control system itself supports up to 5 different network connections, making it suitable for a Modbus TCP implementation. The control software had this

protocol already implemented, and the control program could be extended by using the corresponding blocks from the included library.

The modular DAB3 converter, however, was never designed to communicate by any other interface than its USB connection. As this was making the converter hard to control, the manufacturer of the control system was asked to build a communication card for its system. The control software was then altered to include the newly designed features, making the control system also accessible by Modbus TCP.

Similar to the modular DAB3 converter, the remaining converters were also not equipped with a suitable network interface. Instead of replacing the actual control system of every converter, it was decided to put a small interface converting PCB in between Grid Server and device. To keep the costs to a minimum, the concept consisted of a STM32 microcontroller board bought directly from ST Microelectronics. These boards contain the actual microcontroller, a USB interface for programming, as well as the necessary Ethernet connection. The board is then plugged on top of a base-board which features the drivers for additional communication interfaces like CAN and RS485. It was also planned to make the interface converting PCB as versatile as possible by adding a small amount of digital inputs and outputs as well as analog inputs. Figure 11 shows the planned to use microcontroller board from ST Microelectronics.

Figure 11: STM32 MCU board with Ethernet capability.

Shortly after starting the development of the self-built interface converter board, it turned out that the concept cannot meet two additional key points. The first point is that the board should be mounted on a DIN rail, as this makes mounting the board inside the individual converters much easier. The second point was the programming itself. Because microcontrollers are usually programmed on register level, the code might be hard to understand without deeper knowledge of the register functions. It was debated, that a more high-level programming approach would suit the needs better, and a replacement was investigated to overcome these two issues.

The solution that could overcome the two aforementioned points was found in Beckhoff CX7000 series embedded computers. These systems were originally designed for low-frequency control and safety applications, finding their use in all sorts of use-cases like industrial process control. Besides their network port, depending on their type, these systems come with the additional interface that is needed for interfacing the converters. Programming is done in TwinCAT, which bundles project management, programming and debugging. After ordering the embedded computers, it was found out that the CX7000 series only supported the Modbus protocol running on a serial communication interface. Therefore, the Beckhoff internal ADS interface was also implemented into the Grid Server. A full overview how the individual systems are connected to the Grid Server is given in Table 6.

Two different types of embedded computers were ordered, one type with CAN bus interface to connect to the 3-level ac to dc converters, and the other type with RS485 interface to connect to the remaining dc to dc converter. As those systems bring a small number of additional inputs and outputs, they can also be used to read in door contacts and other auxiliary applications.

Device	Connection
2.5 MVA AFE	Proprietary
5 MW IGBT DAB3	Modbus TCP
Modular DAB3	Modbus TCP
DAB1	Beckhoff CX7080, ADS to RS232
LVDC AFEs	Beckhoff CX7050, ADS to CAN
MVDC Switchgears	Modbus TCP

Table 6: Device connection types.

3.4 Grid Server Computer

To make the Grid Server accessible to any operator, the application was designed to run on a separate computer which should be permanently mounted in the German pilot test hall. Performance test of the Grid Server had shown that the overall processing power was minimal. However, to allow for network separation, the computer needed at least two network ports. Furthermore, a mounting option inside a cabinet was specified as well as 24 V input voltage. To meet these criteria, a small Beckhoff industrial computer was ordered.

4 Grid Protection

The protection of both low and medium voltage grids is another key component in preparing the German pilot grid for safe and reliable operation. For this, the four individual grids have to be considered separately, as they all require different protection schemes and equipment. Furthermore, some grid parts were installed with other commercial test-benches, which have to be checked against the planned operations.

4.1 Low Voltage AC

The low voltage ac part is the easiest grid part to protect, as standard fuses and switches for 400 V ac can be used. Every converter connected to this grid is therefore equipped with fuses of matching current rating. In addition, an external release switch connected to an emergency stop button can be used to disconnect the grid in case of a fault. A mechanical, hand-operated, switch can disconnect the ac grid fully from its supply line. The ac grid is distributed further by the use of a small cabinet with copper bars inside. Two rotary switches allow disconnection of the connected converter systems.

4.2 Medium Voltage AC

With the installation of the GE test-bench, the medium voltage ac connection was also built up. It was originally designed to connect the 2.5 MW AFE to 3.3 kV ac. The MVAC connection is only protected by a MVAC switchgear from SIEMENS, which is externally controlled by the GE test-bench. There is no manual operation possible. The switchgear itself measures voltage and current of the grid, and opens the breaker inside in case of a fault.

As the system was built up commercially, it was left unchanged, and no further modifications were done to the MVAC grid protection.

4.3 DC Grids

The protection of the dc grid parts started by investigation of the different fault types. In general, there are two main fault types, which are control based and hardware based ones. A control-based fault would be for example an overvoltage caused by any converter feeding too much power into one node. On the other hand, a hardware related fault might be an insulation failure.

As any converter can only transfer power within its capabilities, overvoltage is the only fault type considered in this category. It is handled by measuring the node voltage by every converter, so that a faulty measurement of one or multiple (but not all) devices cannot affect the protection scheme. Any converter which registers an overvoltage at one of its sides can then break the grid operation, and therefore interrupt the power flow into this node. To make sure that every converter can protect the grid, all systems are connected to a fault loop system (Section 4.4). Due to the small size of the grid, opening the fault loop then stops operation in the whole grid.

On the hardware side, two types of faults were considered, namely short circuit between poles or ground and open line. In case of an open or broken line, the voltage on the power feeding side would rise and the same protection mechanism as for control-based faults would apply. A

line that opens during operation, however, could not be detected if the arcing voltage is within a certain threshold. For LVDC, this is not problematic, as this grid part is fully placed inside the PGS test-hall. As no external forces are applied to the cables there, a cable connection can only break by overheating it. This is prevented by the use of decent sized cables on all converters.

The short circuit fault type needs to be split up again into pole to pole and pole to ground faults. As all converters are of a galvanic isolated topology or have additional isolation, a pole to ground fault would only shift the potential of both poles in reference to earth. If the converter can withstand that higher voltage against earth, the grid could be operated even with that fault still applied. For the German pilot, the insulation of each converter as well as the cables are rated for this kind of overvoltage. However, due to safety restrictions, operation with a present fault should be avoided. Therefore, the voltage against ground is measured for every node, and the fault loop is interrupted in case of any overvoltage.

Lastly, the grid needs to be protected against overcurrent in case of a pole-to-pole fault. As the dc link capacitors will discharge into a fault of this kind, the overcurrent can be measured and the converters will turn off, avoiding additional power transfer into the fault as well as overloading the semiconductor switches. In addition, the GE converter system is equipped with fast-blowing dc current interruption fuses.

For the other converters in the MVDC part, the impact of a pole-to-pole fault is analyzed in respect to the converter. Figure 12 shows the two distinct phases of a dc fault. During the first phase, the dc link capacitors discharge into the fault while the fault current rises to its maximum. The current charges the parasitic line inductance or any other inductive components in the grid. When the voltage at the dc link capacitor reaches 0 V, the second phase of a dc fault starts. Now, the fault current starts to flow through the free-wheeling diodes of the converter, and a slow decay of the fault current occurs. This current can break the free-wheeling diodes due to hitting the I^2t limit of the devices.

Figure 12: DC fault current and voltage shape.

Comparing the I^2t values of different devices, press-pack diodes show a much higher value than those used in IGBT power modules. This is due to three factors, actual larger die size, no bonding wires that can melt, and better cooling due to the press-pack design. Therefore, it was proposed that converters could be equipped with additional freewheeling diodes, which take over the current in case of a dc fault. Test with artificial short circuits have proven this concept, and a significant reduction in I^2t could be observed for the actual IGBT modules. Figure 13 shows the 100 kW DAB1 converter with additional press-pack diodes mounted directly at the

dc link contacts for low stray inductance. A schematic of the modified DAB1 converter is given in Figure 14.

Figure 13: DAB1 MV side with additional press-pack diodes in foreground.

Figure 14: Schematic of the DAB1 converter with additional free-wheeling diodes.

For the LVDC part, the grid can be protected by dc fuses, which are commercially available from different suppliers. As for the MVDC side, fast acting fuses specifically designed to protect semiconductors should be used. In addition to the dc fuses, a solid-state low voltage dc circuit breaker was proposed. Key to such a breaker is a fast fault current detection to avoid overloading the main breaking semiconductor switch. The detection method was therefore proposed to be split into two measuring methods. For low-speed current rise, the current can be measured with a hall based current sensor. This also allows the measurement of pure dc currents. For fast rising currents beyond the bandwidth of normal hall based sensors, an induction-based sensor can be used. Given that the current rises faster during a fault than under normal operating conditions, the induced voltage can be compared against a reference value. Both sensor types have the advantage of being galvanically isolated against the main conductor, allowing their application in MVDC as well.

The layout of the proposed circuit breaker is shown in Figure 15 and consists of two IGBT modules. While one is the actual current breaking switch, the other acts as a free-wheeling diode. This reduces the overvoltage stress of the switching IGBT, as only the energy stored in the inductive components between breaker and converter has to be dissipated. However, a small varistor is still needed over the main switching IGBT.

Figure 15: LVDC circuit breaker concept.

The LVDC solid-state circuit breaker was investigated and build up inside a small electrical cabinet. Due to its unidirectional design, at least two of these devices are required to protect a line. Any additional converter connected to this line would require an additional breaker. This would rise the protection costs to an unnecessary high level, and with the availability of dc fuses and no necessity of continuous operation it was decided that only dc fuses should protect the LVDC grid part.

4.4 FPGA Based Safety Loop

To interconnect the individual converters and allow for fast turn-off of the German pilot grid in case of an emergency, a safety loop is introduced. This loop should connect every converter, and opening it would be considered as an emergency stop. Due to the placement of the converters and planned future extensions, the loop was changed to a star topology, with a central controller in the middle. The controller itself is FPGA based, and the code was simulated beforehand. To allow for galvanic isolation, the individual converters communicate with a bidirectional fiber optic interface. Losing one of these interfaces would automatically lead to an emergency stop as well.

All converters were equipped with corresponding receiver units, which were tied into the safety loops of each converter. Opening a safety loop would prohibit the converter from switching, effectively turning off the grid. The main controller (Figure 16) was placed into a small case and mounted inside the control room. The individual connection to each converter can be permanently turned off by a manual switch, and the board allows for further extension to more converters. It can also be equipped with a network connection if needed.

Figure 16: FPGA based safety loop.

5 Grid Operations

In this chapter, the actual setup of the grid including all converters and switchgears is discussed. As all converters were modified in software and hardware to interface correctly with the Grid Server application, each device was commissioned and fully tested again. Furthermore, the electrical connection between the individual devices has to be established. Exemplary, the commissioning and testing of two converters is shown here.

5.1 DAB1 Converter

The DAB1 Converter was mostly modified in software to implement the unified converter control structure. For this, the control system code was partially rewritten and extended to new operating modes. Furthermore, the converter state-machine was modified to account for newly defined states as well as to include the safety loop. To interface with the Grid Server, the Beckhoff embedded computer was set up and programmed. In this converter, the serial interface was used for communication, and a lightweight request-respond protocol was implemented on both systems. Lastly, the control board FPGA was reprogrammed to directly interact with the safety loop. This allows the safety loop to directly interrupt the gate signal generation and therefore stopping converter operation within one microsecond.

To verify the operation of the new control modes, the control parameters were tested in simulation first. Afterwards, the converter was fully tested with low voltage where possible. The stability of controlled output voltages was investigated, and load steps were applied to the converter to verify stable operation. Figure 17 shows a load step applied to the low voltage in voltage-control mode.

Figure 17: DAB1 converter load step at LVDC side.

During testing, the converter was first operated from its old control software. This reduced debugging time, as only electrical issues have to be taken into account. With the electrical behavior tested, the communication scheme was changed towards the Grid Server, and the different operating modes were selected from the Grid Editor software. Lastly, the converter

was connected with new cables to the other converters in the grid.

5.2 IGBT DAB3 Converter

The first task of commissioning the 5 MW DAB3 converter was the implementation of an external communication interface. For this, the software running on the GE system offered multiple options. At first, the CAN bus interface was selected to be the most promising option, as this interface is easy to use on the control software side. In addition, synergetic effects were expected on the Grid Server communication side. However, the given software could not be extended with the appropriate driver for the CAN bus communication card. Therefore, Modbus TCP was selected for implementation, which had no actual documentation of the interface implementation but was used in other parts of the converter software. Figure 18 shows the programming interface of the GE system.

Figure 18: GE P80i programming interface.

The software of the converter was further updated to allow for different operating modes and external control. Figure 19 shows the structure of the additional control blocks which were created inside the P80i programming interface. For security reasons, the pulse release for the semi-conductors can still be overwritten by the systems control software to prohibit switching.

Figure 19: Newly created control blocks for IGBT DAB3.

As for all other converters in the grid, the GE 5 MW DAB3 converter was also tested completely, starting with low voltage. During this test it turned out that the newly designed power control suffered from major instabilities due to the systems high dead time and high power in

comparison to the other converters. These instabilities also affected the voltage control, as the underlying current control is shared. Further investigation showed that the transferred power is not monotonously rising while the phase shift is within the dead-time of the converter. However, due to this dead-time, the converter can run in quasi voltage control mode by just switching with zero phase shift between the two converter sides. The voltage on both sides is always 1:1 in this mode. Any deviation leads to a power flow to the side of less voltage.

Figure 20: IGBT DAB3 waveforms; ac current (green), primary side transformer voltage (yellow), secondary side transformer voltage (blue), dc current (purple).

In addition, the 5 MW DAB3 converter was tested with higher power by forcing the phase shift by hand. Figure 20 shows measurements of ac currents and voltages, which were taken during one of these tests. The characteristic voltage and current waveforms of a dual active bridge can clearly be seen. In this operating mode, the converter showed good behavior during lower power, but an increasing voltage imbalance within the split dc-link occurred at power levels higher than 600 kW. This imbalance prohibited the converter to transfer even more power, and further investigation had shown that manual adjustment of additional duty-cycle parameters can balance the dc-link. Furthermore, the imbalance causes transformer saturation, which then leads to additional imbalance again. As this topic is beyond the scope of WP 7.1 and the transferred power in the aforementioned operating mode is sufficient for grid operation, the imbalance is not further investigated here.

5.3 Potential Grid Structures

In this section, the structure of the hybrid ac dc grid during operation should be discussed. Figure 21 shows the proposed connection as well as the used converters. Unfortunately, the modular converter was not operational due to an unforeseen electrical issue, which could not be fixed until the end of WP 7.1.

Figure 21: Grid structure as presented during RWTH demo-site workshop in September 2023.

The medium voltage dc section of the grid is connected with the GE 2.5 MVA AFE to the 3.3 kV ac grid. It can feed power directly through switch 1 to the DAB1 converter, which then transfers power to the LVDC part. The IGBT DAB3 converter can act as an additional galvanic isolation with switches 2 and 3 closed. Lastly, switches 4 and 5 allow a power flow through the FEN dc grid, which can also feed power in a loop for high power testing of the IGBT DAB3 converter (switches 1,4 and 5 closed). The MVDC section is always powered up by the GE testbench system to avoid error states in the corresponding controller. Precharging from the LVDC side can be done when the AFE is not used. The voltage in the MVDC section is always controlled by the AFE if used. When the IGBT DAB3 converter is also used, the voltage at the second node is controlled by this system.

In the LVDC section, the DAB1 converter is directly connected to the two LVAC AFEs. In addition, a switchable resistor bank (not shown in Figure 21) allows for controlled but abrupt changes in power consumption at this node. The voltage at this point is controlled by the DAB1 converter, which can be either in normal voltage control mode or droop control mode. In addition, this converter can precharge the node prior to operation, which is more efficient than using the precharge resistors of the LVAC AFEs.

All different switch positions in the MVDC section as well as different operating points were simulated beforehand for safe grid operation. Figure 22 shows the simulation model from Deliverable WP4.7 (2023), which was used for pre-operation simulation. The conducted simulation proved a successful operation under all selected operation modes.

5.4 Hybrid Grid Testing

After all simulations and commissioning of the converters was finished, the systems were connected together into a hybrid grid. Testing was started with the MVDC section, precharged by the 2.5 MVA AFE, and connected to the DAB1 converter (Figure 23). In this test, stability of the MVDC voltage was verified and functionality of all used converters was checked. Afterwards, the LVDC side was charged up by the DAB1 converter, and stability of the output voltage was checked again. In the same test, discharge and shutdown of the two converters was also tested.

Figure 22: Hybrid grid simulation model from Deliverable WP4.7 (2023).

Figure 23: Test setup with 2.5 MVA AFE and DAB1 converter.

For the next step, the two LVAC AFEs were connected to the DAB1, forming the grid shown in Figure 21. The grid was tested with the same procedure as described above. In addition, the two LVAC AFEs were put into operation, and set-points for power transfer were given from the Grid Editor. The stability of the grid was then tested with both power transfer directions.

In the same setup, the FEN DC grid was also set up and connected directly to the 2.5 MVA AFE. During operation, the power flow was redirected by the MVDC switchgears to use the grid for power transfer. As before, grid stability was checked during the operation.

As a last test, the 5 MW DAB3 converter was connected to the grid. Figure 21 shows the final grid structure, as it was tested and presented during the RWTH demo site workshop meeting in September 2023. Again, the grid was tested with various power flows and connection schemes.

5.5 RWTH Demo-Site Workshop September 2023

During the RWTH workshop meeting in September 2023, the grid was presented in the state shown in Figure 21. The shown converters were interconnected, and grid control was done by hand using the aforementioned Grid Editor and Grid Server software. The grid showed stable and successful operation under the given set-points. Different power flows were presented, and the FEN DC grid was switched in and out of the power flow. During the presentation, several voltage and current measurements were shown to visualize the ongoing operation. Figure 24 shows some impressions of the workshop meeting presentation.

During the RWTH demo site workshop meeting, data was recorded at different measurement points. Figure 25 shows exemplary measurements of the LVAC AFEs ac and dc currents. Dur-

Figure 24: RWTH demo-site workshop meeting in September 2023.

ing this test, the power flow was from MVAC via the 2.5 MVA AFE and through the IGBT DAB3 converter into the MVDC grid. From this grid, the DAB1 converter fed the LVDC side. Power was transferred back into the LVAC grid by the two LVAC AFEs.

Figure 25: Exemplary measurements taken during the RWTH demo-site workshop ac current (red / green / blue), dc current (light blue), dc voltage (purple / yellow).

6 Conclusions

This report describes the RWTH hybrid grid and the work done to allow for new grid setups and validation of grid operation strategies. First, it introduces the RWTH hybrid grid structure and all included devices. For every device, an overview and the main electrical parameters is given. In addition, the status before the start of the workpackage is mentioned. To allow for a centralized control system, the concept of two newly developed applications is introduced, namely the Grid Server and Grid Editor. While the Grid Server handles the underlying data transfer and low level communication between the grid devices, the Grid Editor is used for creating the grid structure and high level control. Furthermore, the implementation of the centralized control structure is described for the individual devices. The report also discusses the used communication interface between the Grid Server and the grid devices.

For safe grid operation, the report investigates different fault scenarios for every grid part. It also gives an overview about the already established protection inside the RWTH hybrid grid and introduces a concept of dc grid protection without the need for separate dc circuit breakers. This concept of placing additional freewheeling diodes near to a converter is also executed on one of the grid devices.

Finally, the report describes the necessary work done for exemplary grid devices before putting them into grid operation. It shows measurements from two different converters during the commissioning phase for grid operation. The report also introduces the final grid structure, as it was used during the RWTH demo-site workshop in September 2023.

References

Canopen standard. (1995). (EN 50325-4, <https://www.can-cia.org/>)

Current os standard. (2024). (<https://currentos.foundation/protocol#voltages>)

Deliverable wp4.7. (2023). (Hyperride WP4.7, Effect of harmonic firewall investigated and verified, doi:10.5281/zenodo.5115579)

Ethernet standard. (2020). (IEEE 802.3)

Rs-485 standard. (1998). (TIA/EIA-485-A Standard, found on <https://www.mikrocontroller.net/attachment/428561/eia485.pdf>)

Thomas, S. (2014). *A medium-voltage multi-level dc/dc converter with high voltage transformation ratio* (PhD thesis). RWTH.

Consortium

Disclaimer

All information provided reflects the status of the HYPERRIDE project at the time of writing and may be subject to change.

Neither the HYPERRIDE Consortium as a whole, nor any single party within the HYPERRIDE Consortium warrant that the information contained in this document is capable of use, nor that the use of such information is free from risk. Neither the HYPERRIDE Consortium as a whole, nor any single party within the HYPERRIDE Consortium accepts any liability for loss or damage suffered by any person using the information.

This document does not represent the opinion of the European Community, and the European Community is not responsible for any use that might be made of its content.

Copyright Notice

© 2024 by the authors, the HYPERRIDE Consortium. This work is licensed under a "CC BY 4.0" license.

